

Tuning Photoluminescence via Entropy Engineering in High Entropy $\text{Re}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ Ceramics

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Abstract

Er^{3+} -doped multicomponent $\text{RE}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ (RE = Y, Lu, Gd, La, and Yb) ceramics with tailored non-equimolar ratios were synthesised via combustion synthesis to explore whether configurational entropy influences their optical properties. The compositions located near the pyrochlore–defect fluorite boundary showed slight structural deviations related to cation-size effects. In contrast, compositions designed to stabilise the defect fluorite structure were readily obtained as single-phase ceramics after sintering at 1650 °C for 4 h in air and served as high, medium, and low entropy model systems. Their luminescent properties indicate that increasing configurational entropy is closely associated with enhanced down-shifting and up-conversion emission compared with the low entropy control sample. These results demonstrate that entropy-guided compositional design enables robust stabilisation of the defect fluorite structure and provides an effective route for improving luminescent performance of Er-doped $\text{RE}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ ceramics.

Keywords

High entropy ceramic, Medium entropy ceramic, Luminescence, $\text{RE}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$

1 Introduction

The development of light-emitting diodes (LEDs), optical devices, plasma display panels, detectors, and scintillators continues to drive the search for advanced phosphor materials [1], [2]. In this context, $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ ceramics (where A denotes trivalent rare-earth cations such as Y^{3+} or Sc^{3+} , and B represents tetravalent cations such as Zr^{4+} , Hf^{4+} , or Ti^{4+}) have emerged as promising host matrices. Their large unit cells offer several advantages: easier substitution of host ions by dopants, reduced lattice strain from size mismatch, higher dopant solubility without phase separation, minimised concentration quenching through optimal spacing of activators, and accommodation of larger dopant ions. These features make them attractive for precise doping control, high luminescence efficiency, and thermal stability, especially in multicomponent systems [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]. In addition, $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ ceramics exhibit

excellent thermal and chemical stability, high melting point, and favourable thermal conductivity and expansion, supporting use in high-temperature or aggressive environments [4], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13].

Despite these advantages, commercial use is hindered by poor toughness [9], [10], [11] and the need for very high sintering temperatures [14], [15], [16]. To address these issues, recent research has explored the high entropy concept. High Entropy Ceramics (HECs), composed of at least five different cations or anions, typically form a single-phase structure stabilised by configurational entropy. This approach not only promotes phase stability [17], [18], [19], [20], but also enhances mechanical, thermal, and chemical properties [20], [21], [22], while potentially reducing sintering temperatures.

$A_2B_2O_7$ ceramics can crystallise in two lattice types: pyrochlore (Fd-3m) and defect fluorite (Fm-3m). The stabilised phase is largely dictated by the ionic radius ratio between A^{3+} and B^{4+} cations (R_C). When $R_C > 1.45$, pyrochlore is favoured; when $R_C < 1.45$, defect fluorite dominates [4], [13], [16], [23], [24], [25]. In multicomponent systems, however, this rule may not apply due to segregation or local distortions [14]. Moreover, processing conditions strongly influence the outcome, with high temperatures driving pyrochlore-to-fluorite transformation. Thus, both cation choice and synthesis parameters are crucial for designing High Entropy Zirconates (HEZs) [9], [11], [24].

Traditionally, control of microstructure through the cation radius ratio has been achieved mainly by element selection [16], [24], [25]. However, the HEC concept also allows non-equimolar compositions, provided that each element is present within a range of 5–35 at. % [18], [26]. This recently explored strategy [9] enables tuning of the radius ratio to stabilise different phases while maintaining overall chemical composition, and can also improve functional properties.

For luminescent applications, this approach offers new opportunities. In HEZ luminophores, luminescent ions form part of the high-entropy composition and are often present at such high concentrations that luminescence quenching occurs. A more flexible method is to introduce the luminescent ions as dopants, as in conventional rare-earth zirconates [3], [4], [12], [27], [28]. To date, this strategy has not been systematically applied to HEZs, and the question whether configurational entropy affects their luminescence performance remains unexplored.

In terms of structure, ordered lattices usually yield stronger luminescence [29], [30], [31], [32]. In $A_2B_2O_7$ ceramics, this corresponds to the pyrochlore phase [4], [33]. Yet its fabrication faces two obstacles: (i) obtaining pure pyrochlore requires very high sintering temperatures (>1800 °C) and/or prolonged dwell times [4], [24], [33], [34], [35]; and (ii) multicomponent systems are prone to segregation, with some cations preferring pyrochlore and others defect fluorite structure [24], [36], [37]. Extended annealing can reduce segregation, but another strategy is to tune the R_C value towards pyrochlore stability. Zhang et al. [16], achieved this by substituting smaller Ti^{4+} for Zr^{4+} at the B-site. However, other studies [38], [39] reported that Ti addition can reduce luminescence. For this reason, attention has increasingly shifted towards defect fluorite phases [23], [40], which are easier to stabilise in multicomponent compositions despite their lower luminescence efficiency.

Consequently, this study aims to clarify whether, and to what extent, chemical disorder affects the luminescence of Er-doped multicomponent zirconates. Specifically, non-equimolar compositions $\text{Er}_{0.02}\text{RE}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ (RE = Y, Lu, Gd, La, Yb in various ratios) are used to stabilise both pyrochlore and defect fluorite phases, thereby testing predictions from the literature. The prepared ceramics are assessed for chemical homogeneity and phase purity, and in structurally single-phase samples, the influence of compositional complexity on luminescence behaviour is carefully examined. By combining non-equimolar compositions with targeted doping, this work provides new insight into the potential of configurational entropy to tune the optical performance of advanced phosphor materials.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material preparation

Y_2O_3 (SkySpring Nanomaterials, USA, purity 99.9%, particle size 100 – 500 nm), Lu_2O_3 (Nanochemazone, Canada, purity 99.9%, nanoparticles), Gd_2O_3 (Verochem, purity 99%, nanoparticles), La_2O_3 (Inframat, USA, purity 99.995%, nanoparticles), Yb_2O_3 (MkNano, Canada, purity 99.5%, particle size 90 nm), and $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Lach-Ner, Czech Republic, purity 98%) were used as reactants for combustion synthesis. Rare-earth oxides and ZrOCl_2 were dissolved separately in diluted nitric acid (1:1) and heated (150 °C on the hotplate) to obtain a clear aqueous solution containing rare-earth nitrates and zirconyl nitrate. Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (TRIS, 98% purity, Lach-Ner, Czech Republic) was dissolved in deionised water and added to the clear solution. The mixture was heated to 150 °C to remove excess water. Following volatilisation, the resulting gel was subjected to heating at 300 °C, where auto-ignition initiated an exothermic combustion process. After combustion, the obtained powder was transferred into a crucible and put in a muffle furnace at 800 °C for 3 hours to remove any carbon residua. The obtained powder was subsequently calcined at 1400 °C for 1 h.

The synthesised powder was deagglomerated by milling in deionised water with zirconia balls (1:2) for 24 h. The colloidal system was dried in a spray dryer to prepare globular granules. The obtained powder was uniaxially pressed to form discs 12 mm in diameter. Subsequently, the discs were pressed in a cold isostatic press (CIP) at 700 MPa for 5 min. Finally, pressed discs were sintered in an electrical furnace (Clasic, Czech Republic) with MoSi_2 heating elements at 1650 °C for 4 h in air. Relative density between 92% and 96% was achieved for all samples, measured using the Archimedes method with theoretical density calculated from X-ray diffraction patterns.

2.2 Characterisation of structural and luminescence properties

The phase composition and crystal structure of the bulk samples were characterised using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Rigaku, Japan). The XRD was operated at a voltage of 40 kV and a current of 30 mA, the source of X-rays was Cu anode (Cu $K\alpha$ radiation). The microstructure of polished and thermally etched (1500 °C for 5 min) surfaces of sintered ceramic discs was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, MIRA3 XMU, Tescan, Czech Republic).

Energy-Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) was conducted to analyse the elemental distribution using SEM equipment. The excitation (PLE) and emission (PL) photoluminescent spectra were recorded on calcinated powders and bulk ceramics using a Fluorolog FL3-21 spectrometer (Horiba Jobin Yvon, France) in backscattering mode at room temperature. An Xe-lamp (450 W) was employed as an excitation light source in UV-VIS spectral region. For recording the up-conversion photoluminescence (UC-PL) spectra, a continuous wave diode laser with a wavelength of 980 nm and the excitation power of 500 mW/cm² was used as an excitation source. The signal was monitored using a photodiode detector PPD-900 (Hamamatsu photomultiplier tube) and corrected for spectrometer and lamp response.

2.3 Design of multicomponent RE₂Zr₂O₇

To induce photoluminescence, the predominantly optically inactive rare-earth (RE) sites must be complemented by photoluminescent (PL) active elements, typically introduced as dopants and co-dopants. Many rare-earth elements exhibit numerous well-defined electronic energy levels that allow excitation and radiative relaxation processes, resulting in luminescent behaviour. In contrast, only four (or six) elements—Sc, Y, La, and Lu—are considered optically inactive, with Gd and Yb sometimes also included, since their energy levels (simple energy level scheme compared to other RE ions) are accessible only in the UV and NIR regions, respectively [41], [42], [43].

In this work, the well-established Er/Yb co-doping system was employed to facilitate comparison with previous reports. The co-doping ratio was set at 1:5, following the approach of Cong et al. [28]. Yb, acting as the sensitizer, was incorporated into the multicomponent lattice at a minimum concentration of 5 at. % (corresponding to an atomic fraction of ≥ 0.1 in a five-element system). Er, the primary activator, was introduced at a substantially lower concentration. Y, Lu, Gd and La were selected as the optically inactive host elements.

The final phase composition—pyrochlore or defect fluorite—was controlled by systematically varying the molar ratios of the selected rare-earth (RE) elements. Yttrium and lutetium exhibit a strong preference for the defect fluorite structure, whereas lanthanum promotes formation of the pyrochlore phase. Gadolinium, positioned near the compositional boundary between the two structures, exhibits intermediate behaviour [25], [44], [45], [46], [47]. The R_C value was calculated using the weighted average ionic radius of the RE³⁺ ions $\overline{R_A}$

$$\overline{R_A} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{x_i}{0.4} \cdot R_i}{5} \quad (1)$$

where x_i stands for the mole fraction of the i^{th} element and R_i is the ionic radius of the i^{th} element in oxidation state 3+ and Coordination Number (CN) equal to VIII. According to the mentioned rules, the following compositions were designed (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Designed composition of $RE_2Zr_2O_7$ multicomponent ceramics.

Sample	Composition	R_C	Targeted phase	ΔS_{conf}
HEC - P	$Er_{0.02}:(Y_{0.48}Lu_{0.4}Gd_{0.3}La_{0.7}Yb_{0.1})Zr_2O_7$	1.48	Pyrochlore	1.51R
HEC - DF	$Er_{0.02}:(Y_{0.58}Lu_{0.5}Gd_{0.5}La_{0.3}Yb_{0.1})Zr_2O_7$	1.44	Defect Fluorite	1.53R
MEC-DF	$Er_{0.02}:(Y_{0.68}Lu_{0.6}Gd_{0.5}La_{0.1}Yb_{0.1})Zr_2O_7$	1.40	Defect Fluorite	1.42R
Control-DF	$Er_{0.02}:(Y_{1.88}Yb_{0.1})Zr_2O_7$	1.42	Defect Fluorite	0.51R

[#]HEC = High-Entropy ceramics; MEC = Medium-Entropy Ceramics

3 Results and discussion

The multicomponent $RE_2Zr_2O_7$ ceramics were synthesised via combustion synthesis and subsequently densified by conventional sintering. Luminescent properties were evaluated for both the calcined powders and the bulk ceramics. Phase purity was assessed by X-ray diffraction, while microstructural homogeneity and elemental distribution were examined by scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy on the sintered bulk samples.

3.1 Evaluation of homogeneous element distribution in HECs

3.1.1 Elemental distribution in pyrochlore and defect fluorite structure

Single-phase homogeneity is essential in multicomponent systems, requiring uniform integration of all constituents [18], [19], [20], [28], [48], [49]. To investigate this, energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was conducted. **Figure 1a** illustrates the EDS results for the sintered sample, designed with an R_C value tailored for the pyrochlore structure (HEC – P). Pronounced La enriched areas are evident, likely due to the sample's proximity to the phase transformation boundary between pyrochlore and defect fluorite (highlighted by the blue circle in **Figure 1b**, as determined by the experimental parameters. Consequently, elements favouring the defect fluorite structure (Y, Lu, Yb, eventually Gd) are already incorporated into the fluorite-like phase.

This behaviour was also reported by Zhang et al. [14], who prepared transparent $(LaNdSmGdYb)_2Zr_2O_7$ ceramics. In back-scattered electron SEM images, they identified two distinct regions: EDS point analysis revealed that the lighter areas contained higher Yb concentrations, whereas the darker regions were enriched in La, consistent with our findings. A similar La and Yb segregation has also been observed in binary $RE_2Zr_2O_7$ ceramics [36], [50].

Figure 1: (a) EDS map of $Er_{0.02}:(Y_{0.48}Lu_{0.4}Gd_{0.3}La_{0.7}Yb_{0.1})Zr_2O_7$ (HEC - P); (b) Diagram of phase stability in $RE_2Zr_2O_7$ ceramics [24], [51] with marked parameters, which were used.

The presence of two phases was also confirmed by XRD analysis (**Figure 2**). The relatively low intensity of the pyrochlore diffraction maxima suggested that it exists only as a minor phase compared to the dominant defect fluorite phase. Rietveld's analysis confirmed that the sample contained 94% of the defect fluorite phase and only 6% of the pyrochlore. The findings are consistent with the EDS maps (**Figure 1a**), where La-rich areas were relatively scarce. Hence, the $RE_2Zr_2O_7$ ceramic with pyrochlore structure was not successfully prepared by this simple route.

Figure 2: XRD pattern of sintered HEC - P sample at 1650 °C for 4 hours.

The issue of element segregation is usually solved by replacing segregated elements with more suitable ones for the target structure, as demonstrated in numerous publications. For instance, Zhao et al. [52] investigated $(\text{La}_{0.2}\text{Ce}_{0.2}\text{Nd}_{0.2}\text{Sm}_{0.2}\text{Eu}_{0.2})_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ ceramic. As it is obvious, they used only larger elements, favouring the pyrochlore structure. Therefore, no segregation was detected, and the single-phase structure was confirmed by XRD measurements, showing only diffraction maxima characteristic for the pyrochlore structure.

Zhang et al. [16] incorporated La, Gd, Y, Yb and Er at the RE position. This combination is closer to the system studied in this work, containing cations that favour either the defect fluorite (Y, Yb, Er) or pyrochlore (La) structure. The results confirmed the influence of cation size on the phase purity. In addition, the authors also partially substituted the Zr^{4+} cations with much smaller Ti^{4+} cations. At higher Ti^{4+} concentration, the microstructure transformed from single-phase defect fluorite to pyrochlore, confirming the relevance of the cation ratio (R_C) rule, since increasing amount of Ti^{4+} raised the R_C value.

In the present study, the second HEC was designed to comply with the R_C values that stabilise the defect fluorite structure (HEC-DF). In contrast to the HEC-P sample, EDS analysis of HEC-DF confirmed a homogeneous distribution of constituent elements (**Figure 3a**). The existence of single-phase structure can be attributed to two factors: (i) the composition lies well within the defect fluorite stability domain, thus avoiding phase transformations (**Figure 1b**); and (ii) the reduced La content in HEC-DF facilitates the incorporation of La into the less favourable DF phase.

Figure 3: EDS map of (a) HEC-DF, (b) MEC-DF and (c) Control-DF sample.

3.1.2 Elemental distribution in defect fluorite structures with varying entropy levels

To enable comparison and to evaluate the effect of entropy level on luminescent behaviour, a control sample (Control – DF), and a medium-entropy variant (MEC – DF), were synthesised using the same preparation route (**Table 1**). As shown in **Figure 3b** and **3c**, both compositions exhibited homogeneous microstructures, as confirmed by EDS mapping. Furthermore, XRD analysis confirmed that all three samples corresponded to the defect-fluorite structure, as only its characteristic reflections were observed (see **Figure 4**).

Figure 4: XRD patterns of sintered bulk samples at 1650 °C for 4 hours.

The graph in the **Figure 5a** shows refined lattice parameters of prepared samples with the defect fluorite structure, obtained from Rietveld refinement of XRD data, and the lattice parameter of $Y_2Zr_2O_7$ sample reported by Nandi et al. [46], representing the undoped sample. The lattice parameters of $Y_2Zr_2O_7$, Control-DF and MEC-DF were identical. At the first sight, this result appears counterintuitive, since most studies [24], [25], [52], [53], [54] reported that incorporation of additional elements usually led to an increase or decrease in lattice parameters, reflected by the shifts of XRD diffraction maxima to lower or higher angles.

The calculation of the weighted average cation radii for the rare-earth (RE) sites (**Table 2**) revealed that it was almost identical for all three samples $Y_2Zr_2O_7$, Control-DF, and MEC-DF. It appeared that the variations in cation sizes (illustrated in **Figure 5b**), combined with their respective concentrations balanced each other, resulting in negligible impact on the lattice parameters.

In contrast, the HEC – DF sample exhibited a slightly larger lattice parameter compared to other samples, attributed to a higher lanthanum content, which replaced smaller lutetium and yttrium cations. This observation was supported by the weighted average cation radii for the RE sites, where HEC – DF showed a slightly higher value than the other samples (**Table 3**).

Figure 5: (a) Lattice parameters of the prepared samples. Y₂Zr₂O₇ lattice parameter was measured in Ref. [46]. (b) Cation diameters of incorporated rare-earth elements - the diameters are for elements with CN = VIII and oxidation state 3+ in pm.

Table 2: Weighted average radii of elements occupying RE position in RE₂Zr₂O₇ ceramics.

Composition	Weighted average RE elements radii [pm]
Y ₂ Zr ₂ O ₇	102
Control – DF: Er _{0.02} :(Y _{1.88} Yb _{0.1})Zr ₂ O ₇	~ 102
MEC – DF: Er _{0.02} :(Y _{0.68} Lu _{0.6} Gd _{0.5} La _{0.1} Yb _{0.1})Zr ₂ O ₇	~ 102
HEC – DF: Er _{0.02} :(Y _{0.58} Lu _{0.5} Gd _{0.5} La _{0.3} Yb _{0.1})Zr ₂ O ₇	~ 104

The used composition design approach targeting the DF compositional space without phase transformation (see **Figure 1b**), appears to be an effective method by which single-phase microstructures with a general formula of RE₂Zr₂O₇ can be prepared in multicomponent systems.

3.2 Luminescence

The photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra (not shown here) recorded while monitoring the emission at 1530 nm revealed the most intense peak at approximately 378 nm in all studied

samples, corresponding to ${}^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{11/2}$ transition. Moreover, well-known absorption spectra of Er/Yb co-doped systems show an intensive absorption peak around 980 nm, corresponding to ${}^2F_{7/2} \rightarrow {}^2F_{5/2}$ transition [28], [55], [56], [57]. Therefore, these wavelengths were used to excite the samples and to study emission response.

Figure 6 shows the photoluminescence emission (PL) and up-conversion (UC) spectra of the HEC–DF sample under excitation at 378 nm and 980 nm. The PL spectrum, recorded under 378 nm excitation (**Figure 6a**) shows characteristic emission peaks typical for Er^{3+} ions [28], [57], [58], observed at 407, 524, 550 and 660 nm, corresponding to ${}^2H_{9/2}$, ${}^2H_{11/2}$, ${}^4S_{3/2}$, and ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transitions, respectively. The green emission significantly dominates over red and blue emissions when the sample is excited at 378 nm.

Figure 6c shows the UC emission spectrum of the HEC–DF sample under 980 nm excitation. Although the characteristic Er^{3+} spectral pattern closely resembles that of the down-shifting spectrum presented in Figure 6a, the green-to-red intensity ratio (G/R ratio) has changed significantly. The down-shifting spectrum is dominated by green emission, whereas the UC spectrum exhibits a strongly enhanced red emission. This change in the G/R ratio can be rationalised in terms of the energy-level scheme and mechanism underlying the down-shifting (DS) and UC processes (**Figure 7**).

Figure 1: (a) Emission spectrum of HEC - DF under 378 nm excitation; (b) up-conversion spectrum of HEC - DF sample under 980 nm excitation.

Under near ultraviolet (NUV) excitation at 378 nm, the Er^{3+} excited state ${}^4G_{11/2}$ is populated via ground-state absorption (GSA), ${}^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{11/2}$. From this energy level, the electrons relax non-radiatively via multi-phonon relaxation pathways to the ${}^2H_{9/2}$, ${}^2H_{11/2}$ / ${}^4S_{3/2}$, and ${}^4F_{9/2}$ energy levels. Subsequent radiative de-excitation process to the ground state produces blue (${}^2H_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$; ~407 nm), green (${}^2H_{11/2}$ / ${}^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$; ~524/550 nm) and red (${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$) emissions observed in the down-shifting PL spectra. The simplified UC mechanism in Er^{3+} -doped multicomponent zirconates can be described as follows (**Figure 7**). Under 980 nm near infrared (NIR) excitation, electrons in Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions are promoted from the ground states to higher-lying energy levels through ground state absorption (GAS) process: Yb^{3+} : ${}^2F_{7/2} \rightarrow {}^2F_{5/2}$; Er^{3+} : ${}^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{11/2}$ [28], [58], [59], [60], [61], [62]. Because Yb^{3+} ions possess a

much larger absorption cross-section than Er^{3+} ions, the 980 nm photon predominantly populates the $\text{Yb}^{3+} {}^2\text{F}_{5/2}$ level [58]. The energy absorbed by Yb^{3+} is then resonantly transferred (ET) to neighbouring Er^{3+} ions, due to their well-matched energy levels, populating the $\text{Er}^{3+} {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}$ state via ET1: ${}^2\text{F}_{5/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}(\text{Er}^{3+})$. Thus, the $\text{Er}^{3+} {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}$ level is primarily populated through $\text{Yb}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Er}^{3+}$ energy transfer. The excited Er^{3+} ion can then absorb another incident photon either through excited-state absorption (ESA) or via a second energy-transfer process (ET2), populating the $\text{Er}^{3+} {}^4\text{F}_{7/2}$ level: ET2: ${}^2\text{F}_{5/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Er}^{3+})$. Subsequently, non-radiative relaxation from ${}^4\text{F}_{7/2}$ state to the ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ and ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ levels occurs, followed by green UC emission at 524 and 550 nm through the radiative transitions ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}/{}^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$. For the Er^{3+} red UC emission (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$) occurring at about 650-670 nm, two primary pathways are generally considered: (1) direct population of the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ level through non-radiative multi-phonon relaxation from ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}/{}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ states (${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}/{}^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$), or (2) population of the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ level from ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2}$ state either via ESA process (${}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$) and/or through an additional energy transfer process ET3; ET3: ${}^2\text{F}_{5/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{13/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}(\text{Er}^{3+})$. Cross-relaxation (CR) processes within $\text{Er}^{3+}-\text{Er}^{3+}$ ion pairs may also contribute [58]; ${}^4\text{I}_{9/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{13/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}(\text{Er}^{3+})$, ${}^4\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow 2 \times {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}(\text{Er}^{3+})$.

As discussed above, the PL spectra under 378 nm excitation exhibit dominant green emission and only weak red emission, in contrast to the UC spectra where the red emission dominates. This indicates that the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ state, responsible for the red UC emission (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$), is primarily populated either through the ESA process (${}^4\text{I}_{13/2} + h\nu \rightarrow {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$) and/or through the resonant energy transfer ET3 (${}^2\text{F}_{5/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{I}_{13/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}(\text{Er}^{3+})$), rather than by multi-phonon relaxation pathway ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}/{}^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$. In addition to cross-relaxation (CR) processes within $\text{Er}^{3+}-\text{Er}^{3+}$ ion pairs, CR processes involving $\text{Er}^{3+}-\text{Yb}^{3+}$ ion pairs (e.g. ${}^2\text{F}_{7/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{S}_{3/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{13/2}(\text{Er}^{3+}) + {}^4\text{F}_{5/2}(\text{Yb}^{3+})$) may also contribute to the population of the ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2}$ state and subsequently the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ state of Er^{3+} ions. As a result, the preferential population of the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ level via these processes leads to enhanced red UC fluorescence.

Figure 7: Energy level diagram describing the down-conversion and up-conversion process of $\text{Er}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ doped system after 378 and 980 nm excitation. The scheme is inspired by other work [28], [56], [58], [63].

The comparison of DS and UC luminescence in samples with varying configurational entropy (**Figure 8**) shows that both the MEC and HEC compositions exhibit higher emission intensity than the control. At first glance, this appears counterintuitive, since introducing multiple cations into a single lattice generally increases structural disorder, which is often associated with reduced luminescence efficiency [64], [65]. However, high entropy cation mixing can also modify the local environment around Er^{3+} in ways that enhance radiative processes. Variations in ionic radius and polarizability among neighbouring cations alter the local electric field and reduce site symmetry at Er^{3+} sites, increasing the probability of forced electric-dipole 4f–4f transitions. In addition, compositional fluctuations can locally adjust energy-level alignment between the host and Er^{3+} , improving excitation efficiency [30], [31], [66]. Together, these local structural effects can compensate for global disorder and lead to enhanced luminescence in higher-entropy compositions.

This hypothesis can be rationalised by considering the influence of specific cations on the local environment of Er^{3+} . The HEC–DF and MEC–DF samples contain Lu^{3+} ions, whose smaller ionic radius and higher polarizability compared to Y^{3+} produce a stronger local crystal field around Er^{3+} ions. Such variations in local electric field and coordination asymmetry increase the mixing of opposite-parity states in the Er^{3+} 4f manifold, thereby enhancing the probability of forced electric-dipole transitions and contributing to the higher luminescence intensity observed in the HEC/MEC–DF samples compared to the control sample. La may play another important role. Deshmukh et al. [67] reported that incorporating La into $\text{Er}/\text{Yb}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ phosphors reduces both green and red luminescence intensities, while preserving the dominance of red emission above the green one. This result can explain why in the up-conversion emission spectra (**Figure 8b**), the HEC–DF sample containing a higher amount of La exhibits lower

luminescent intensity compared to the MEC–DF sample, despite showing stronger intensity in down-shifting emission (**Figure 8a**). The incorporation of Gd into host matrix can modify the host band gap, therefore influencing the absorption, energy transfer and emission kinetics as was reported by Lu et al. [68]. However, all presented explanations are only hypotheses and further investigation is required.

Figure 8: (a) Down-shifting and (b) Up-conversion emission spectra of Control-DF, MEC-DF and HEC-DF powder samples. (c) Down-shifting and (d) Up-conversion emission spectra of Control-DF, MEC-DF and HEC-DF bulk samples.

Figures 8c and 8d summarise the photoluminescence measurements performed on bulk ceramic samples under 378 nm and 980 nm excitation, respectively. For identical $\text{Er}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ compositions, a pronounced dependence of the emission intensity on the sample morphology (powder versus bulk ceramic) is observed. Under 378 nm excitation, which probes linear down-shifting luminescence, the powder exhibits photoluminescence intensities several times higher than those of the polished bulk ceramic. This behaviour can be attributed to the strong light-scattering characteristics of the powder, which increase the effective optical path length and excitation efficiency, as well as to a more homogeneous distribution of the excitation throughout the powder volume. In contrast, in dense bulk ceramics the high-energy excitation is confined to a shallow near-surface region, resulting in a high local excitation density and enhanced non-radiative losses at the surfaces, grain boundaries, and residual defects, which collectively reduce

the observed emission intensity. As a consequence of this intensity loss, differences in PL intensity between individual compositions are partially suppressed, and the trend of higher PL intensity in samples with increased configurational entropy is only partially preserved.

Under 980 nm excitation, where up-conversion proceeds via nonlinear, multi-photon energy-transfer processes between Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions, the trend is reversed, and the bulk ceramic exhibits significantly stronger up-conversion emission than the powder. Up-conversion efficiency is particularly sensitive to non-radiative relaxation pathways and to the effective lifetimes of the intermediate excited states. In the powder, the high surface-to-volume ratio and the presence of surface-related defects promote non-radiative deactivation, which disproportionately suppresses higher-order up-conversion processes. In contrast, the bulk ceramic provides a more crystalline environment with a reduced relative influence of surface quenching and more efficient energy transfer between Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions, leading to enhanced up-conversion intensity. Under these conditions, the intrinsic advantage of higher-entropy compositions is retained, and bulk samples with increased configurational entropy consistently exhibit higher up-conversion photoluminescence intensities compared with the Control-DF sample.

4 Conclusions

The conventional and multicomponent rare-earth zirconates with the general formula $\text{A}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ and co-doped by the pair Er/Yb were prepared by combustion synthesis. The resulting powders were converted into bulk ceramics through a single-step sintering process. The results demonstrated that the defect fluorite phase is more readily stabilised than the pyrochlore phase. Consequently, luminescent properties of the samples with the inherently disordered defect fluorite structure were investigated.

Samples with higher configurational entropy (MEC-DF and HEC-DF) exhibit greater luminescent intensity than the low-entropy control sample (Control-DF). This finding suggests that the high-entropy design can compensate for, or even overcome, the potential negative impact of structural disorder on luminescence. The improved luminescence is attributed to the local stabilisation of more favourable environments around the luminescent centres. Variations in ionic radii, bonding characteristics, and local electric fields of surrounding cations modulate the crystal field around the luminescent centres, influencing photon absorption, energy transfer, and radiative emission processes—ultimately determining overall luminescence efficiency.

The observed differences between down-conversion and up-conversion emissions are likely related to variations in the concentrations of the incorporated ions and their distribution within the lattice. In particular, La incorporation appears to play a key role, as it strongly influences emission within the red region of the visible spectrum, consistently with previous literature reports.

This study demonstrates that configurational entropy can serve as an effective design parameter for improving luminescent performance in multicomponent ceramics. Further investigation into the individual contributions of specific cations will deepen the mechanistic understanding and

enable targeted optimisation of composition–structure–property relationships for advanced phosphor materials.

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